

A pragmatical analysis of politeness and face problems in 'Pride and Prejudice'

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Abstract

Pragmatics, closely related to literature, has been considered a powerful tool to study the language of literary works. *Pride and Prejudice* is famous British writer Jane Austen's masterpiece. Jane Austin is apt at depicting people by conversations. She subtly use conversations to highlight themes, push forward the plot. The characters created by her are full of dramatic stretching force, reproducing the people's characteristics, emotions and conflicts vividly. Conversation is the main tool to achieve humorous effects as well. Therefore, conversation plays a very important role in Jane Austin's novels. This paper, based on the analysis of *Pride and Prejudice* from the pragmatic viewpoint, reveals distinctive personalities of characters, the feelings of characters and their intentions of social interaction.

Keywords: *Pride and Prejudice*. Cooperative principle. Politeness. Face.

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Introduction

Pride and Prejudice is the representative work of Jane Austen (1775-1817), one of her most popular novels in the late 18th and early 19th century. The language of the book is fresh and smooth, witty and humorous. In this novel, the clever combination of narrative and dialogue narrates the characters in great detail. Each character has a distinct speaking style that reflects their personality. The study in terms of pragmatics provides a new method for analyzing the linguistic features of the novel, and more clearly reflects the relationship between the language form and the language user. This paper will analyze the dialogue between characters from the perspective of pragmatics, namely, the principle of conversational cooperation, the principle of politeness and the theory of face, so that we can accurately understand the intention and behavior of the communicator and gain insight into the social relations between the communicators (He, 2000).

Theoretical Basis

Grice (1975) as cited by Davies (2007) believes that the reason why both parties in a conversation can communicate is that they all abide by some basic principles, which make both parties cooperate with each other in the conversation to achieve the purpose of mutual understanding, which is the Cooperative Principle. The cooperative principle requires that each participant's comments during the conversation be consistent with its goal.

The principle of cooperation contains four criteria: **Quantity Maxim:** discourse provides necessary but not redundant information; **Quality Maxim:** the content of discourse is true; **Relation Maxim:** Say what is relevant to a topic in a particular context; **Manner Maxim:** The manner of expression should be clear, concise and orderly. Grice believes that both parties in communication must abide by these norms to cooperate in a tacit and harmonious manner. If these norms are violated, misunderstandings may occur (Li, 2007).

Sometimes, the conversationalists will deliberately violate the cooperative principles, which may be due to the influence of the politeness principle. Politeness Principle was put forward by G. N. Leech, a famous British scholar, based on Cooperation Principle in 1983. Leech further put forward six Politeness principles that restrict interpersonal communication. They are: **Tact Maxim:** make others lose less and benefit others as much as possible; **Generosity Maxim:** make yourself as little as possible to benefit, as much as possible to lose; **Approbation Maxim:** Try not to belittle others and praise others as much as possible; **Modesty Maxim:** flatter yourself as little as possible and belittle yourself as much as possible; **Agreement Maxim:** minimize the differences between the two sides and maximize the agreement between the two sides; **Sympathy Maxim:** Minimize mutual antipathy and increase mutual sympathy as much as possible (He & Chen, 2004).

From Leech's (1983) Politeness Principle we can draw the following rule: the speaker always tries to do the hearer as much as possible and tries to make the hearer feel respected at the expense of himself. To gain the good impression of the other side is conducive to the smooth communication. Leech believed that the cooperative principle was needed, but could not fully explain the conversational implication, while the politeness principle explained the problems that the cooperative principle could not explain, and the politeness principle was a supplement to the cooperative principle (Sorlin, 2017).

Brown & Levinson (1978) put forward a mature "Face Saving Theory" based on the research of Goffman et al. The "Face Saving Theory" first assumes that people who participate in communication activities are Model persons. The Model Person is "a rational person with face demand", and a person with normal communication ability in the society. The "face" that a Model Person has refers to the "public self-image" that every member of society wants to obtain for himself. "Face" can be divided into negative face and positive face. Negative face refers to that one does not want others to impose on him or her, and his or her behavior is not interfered and hindered by others, that is, it does not violate or hinder the freedom of action of the listener. Positive face refers to the desire to be approved and liked by others, that is, to satisfy the hopes and requests of the listener.

Brown and Levinson (1978) suggested that there are a number of linguistic behaviors that are inherently inconsistent with communicator's face. These are face threatening acts (FTA) (Brown & Levinson, 1978). In verbal communication, sometimes in order to achieve a certain purpose, it is necessary to carry out a speech act that may hurt the other party's face.

People are extremely complex, and the environment of verbal communication, such as the cultural background, age and social status of both parties, is ever-changing, which determines the infinite nature of conversational skills and the instability of their application. In all kinds of communication activities, especially in the case of being FTA, but unwilling or inconvenient to implement FTA to the other party, they often use various conversational skills and intentionally violate the cooperation principle to achieve the purpose of communication. The following paragraphs will illustrate the use of politeness principle and face theory to analyze the violation of cooperation principle in conversational skills. This paper selects typical dialogues from *Pride and Prejudice* and makes a detailed analysis of their conversational implicature by applying the above pragmatic theories.

Analysis of the Dialogues in *Pride and Prejudice*

From the dialogues of the characters in *Pride and Prejudice*, we can see that the norms of cooperation and politeness are violated everywhere. For example, the first chapter of Volume I opens with a dialogue between Mr. and Mrs. Bennett (Austen, 1981):

'My dear Mr. Bennet,' said his lady to him one day, 'have you heard that Netherfield Park is let at last?' (1)

Mr. Bennet replied that he had not.

'But it is,' returned she, 'for Mrs. Long has just been here, and she told me all about it.' (2)

Mr. Bennet made no answer. (3)

'Do not you want to know who has taken it?' cried his wife impatiently. (4)

'You want to tell me, and I have no objection to hearing it.' (5)

'Is he married or single?' (6)

'Oh! single, my dear, to be sure! A single man of large fortune; four or five thousand a year. What a fine thing for our girls!' (7)

'How so? How can it affect them?' (8)

'My dear Mr. Bennet,' replied his wife, 'how can you be so tiresome! You must know that I am thinking of his marrying one of them.' (9)

Learning that the new owner of Netherfield Manor is a rich bachelor, Mrs. Bennett is extremely excited, anxious to tell the news to Mr. Bennett (1) (2) and (4), but the latter reacted coolly, in violation of the Quantity and Agreement Maxims, and did not answer (3), which shows that he is not interested--in this it has affected the Bennett's positive face. He then violated the Manner Maxim (5): Instead of answering his wife's question with a simple Yes or No, he used a complex sentence and a teasing tone. He did not want to hear but to avoid hurting Mrs. Bennett's face too much, he adopted Agreement Maxim to minimize the difference between him and Mrs. Bennett.

When asked by Mr. Bennett about Mr. Bingley's marital status (6), Mrs. Bennett's response (7) was a deliberate violation of Quantity Maxim and Relation Maxim. She gave more information than was necessary, including a description of Bingley's financial situation and seeing Bingley's arrival as a blessing to her daughters. Mrs. Bay said this to try to maximize the consistency between the two sides. Reading into his wife's mind, Mr. Bennett threatened her positive face by pretending not to (8), which violated Agreement Maxim. Through this dialogue, the author shows the two characters' personalities of one being cold and the other being hot. It is no surprise, therefore, that the reader comes to the summary of the couple's characters at the end of the first chapter: Mr. Bennett is eccentric, sarcastic, and a constant threat to Mrs. Bennett's face; Mrs. Bennett is intellectually poor and temperamental.

Look again at Lady Catherine's first conversation with Elizabeth (Chapter 6, Volume 2):

'Upon my word,' said her Ladyship, 'you give your opinion very decidedly for so young a person. —Pray, what is your age?'

'With three younger sisters grown up,' replied Elizabeth smiling, 'your Ladyship can hardly expect me to own it.'

First of all, Mrs. Catherine's question violated Tact Maxim by asking the wrong question, which threatened Elizabeth's negative face. Elizabeth's answer violated Quantity and Tact Maxims, and threatened Mrs. Catherine's positive face, not giving a direct answer. Therefore, the eminent Mrs. Catherine was shocked. Most of the people she talked to were submissive, and only Elizabeth, who was witty and full of character, dared to mock her. Another conversation that clearly violates Agreement Maxim takes place between Darcy and Miss Bingley. In chapter 10 volume I, Darcy writes a letter to his sister Georgiana, while Miss Bingley praises him. Elizabeth overhears this amusing conversation:

'How delighted Miss Darcy will be to receive such a letter!' (1)
He made no answer. (2)

'You write uncommonly fast.' (3)

'You are mistaken. I write rather slowly.' (4)

'How many letters you must have occasion to write in the course of the year! Letters of business too! How odious I should think them!' (5)

'It is fortunate, then, that they fall to my lot instead of to yours.' (6)

'Pray tell your sister that I long to see her.' (7)

'I have already told her so once, by your desire.' (8)

'I am afraid you do not like your pen. Let me mend it for you. I mend pens remarkably well.' (9)

'Thank you — — — but I always mend my own.' (10)

'How can you contrive to write so even?' (11)

He was silent. (12)

'Tell your sister I am delighted to her of her improvement on the harp, and pray let her know that I am quite in raptures with her beautiful little design for a table, and I think it infinitely superior to Miss Grantley's.' (13)

'Will you give me leave to defer your raptures till I write again? At present I have not room to do them justice.' (14)

'Oh ! it is of no consequence. I shall see her in January. But do you always write such charming long letters to her, Mr. Darcy?' (15)

'They are generally long; but whether always charming, it is not for me to determine.' (16)

'It is a rule with me, that a person who can write a long letter with ease, cannot write ill.' (17)

Miss Bingley had always been very fond of Darcy and wasted no time in lavishing compliments. In saying (1), she violated Quality Maxim by supposing, without sufficient evidence, that Miss Darcy would be pleased to receive the letter, but had complied with Approbation Maxim. To this Darcy did not reply (2). He violated Quantity Maxim, Manner Maxim and Agreement Maxim, and thus threatened Miss Bingley's positive face by demonstrating his complete unwillingness to cooperate and to carry on the conversation.

Then Miss Bingley rattled again. In saying (3), she once again violated Quality Maxim by saying something that was not true but using Approbation Maxim. This was immediately pointed out bluntly by Darcy (4), who claimed that he had written slowly. Darcy had once again violated Agreement Maxim and threatened Miss Bingley's positive pride. Miss Bingley therefore changed the subject (5), in which she violated Relevant Maxim to save her face and used Generosity and Sympathy Maxims to show her politeness. In response to this exclamation (6), Darcy violated Manner Maxim by implying that it had nothing to do with her and violated Sympathy Maxim, threatening Miss Bingley's positive face. Miss Bingley's subsequent requests (7) and offers of help (9) were graciously rejected by Darcy (8) (10), which violated Agreement Maxim and threatened Miss Bingley's positive face.

Miss Bingley had come full circle and returned to praise, abiding by Approbation Maxim, in which Darcy was again silent, violating Quantity, Manner and Relevant Maxims. At this point, as it may be said, Darcy's repeated attempts to make Miss Bingley lose face seemed to bring the conversation to an end. But Miss Bingley, still not boring, insisted on continuing the conversation by making two more requests, which were also refused by Darcy.

Instead of being annoyed, she made her own way, and again broke Quality Maxim by praising Darcy for the length and elegance of his letter, in which she had complied with Approbation Maxim. To this, Darcy affirms one and denies the other (16). What makes this conversation interesting is that both sides are violating the principles of cooperation. One was warm, full of flattery; The other was cold and indifferent, a constant threat to the other's face. Their characters and relationships are revealed clearly to the reader.

Conclusion

The relationship between politeness principle and cooperation principle is very close. The cooperation principle plays a role in regulating the content of the two parties in the conversation, which enables the two parties to communicate under the premise of being willing to cooperate. However, politeness principle has a higher regulating effect and is the key to restrict pragmatics. In order to abide by politeness principle, people even have to sacrifice cooperation principle. The cooperation principle and politeness principle have the relationship of mutual blending and mutual restriction. When the politeness principle is violated, the other party's face is threatened and the relationship between the two parties will be affected.

For a certain communicative purpose, the characters in *Pride and Prejudice* often violate the principle of cooperation and politeness, and hurt each other's face, thus creating distinctive characteristics, such as sarcastic Mr. Bennett, arrogant Darcy, overbearing Mrs. Catherine, witty and acerbic Elizabeth and so on.

This paper tries to analyze the conversational implicature of specific examples with the help of the above pragmatic theories, hoping to provide some enlightenment and reference for us to use polite language in real life to keep face of both sides.

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